

UK Covid-19 - Deaths in the Elderly

By Dr. Alan Wenham-Prosser D.Prof., MA.

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Introduction

With the deaths in the UK from the Covid-19 virus being one of the highest in the world, and the UK having a world famous National Health System (NHS), we need to ask the question, “How did 82% of UK deaths become those over 65 years?” The UK is a highly developed country with one of the highest percentages in the world of its population with access to a general medical practitioner (GP) and proximity to modern NHS hospital facilities and a fast acting NHS emergency ambulance system. What has gone wrong so as to make the situation of the elderly in the UK so much at risk from the new virus? Who has really opened up this question with all the relevant information which is to hand, being applied towards an answer? There are many studies; but has anyone ‘joined up the dots’? Also information here maybe relevant elsewhere than the UK.

Note :- Sherlock Holmes is a famous fictional detective who often ‘joined up the dots’ when investigating the various events or elements of a crime; in a common sense approach. During the BBC program “More or Less” on 3rd June 2020, the matter of UK tests for people infected with possible covid-19 was discussed. Jessica Watson, a doctoral researcher at Bristol University UK, presented the various kinds of result. She stated that if a test result showed negative it could be only 70% reliable. Meaning that the patient could still have the virus. The program presenter asked, “What should the person then decide to do?” Jessica said, “Apply the duck test - the saying goes, *‘If it Looks Like a Duck and Quacks Like a Duck, then it is most likely a Duck,’* “ Meaning that if you have the symptoms of a fever, and/or a cough and/or have lost your sense of smell then applying the duck test means it is highly likely that you have corona virus infection. This was the surprising common sense advice from an academic, who is also a GP. Such advice coming from an eminent researcher on the radio is helpful in applying the Sherlock Holmes approach in the research for this paper; where not all evidence can be relied on nor is it readily available. So where in this paper there is even the smallest element of this Holmes approach I have introduced the following acronym in the text [LLD + QLD = D] so as to clarify that the above common sense approach is included in the conclusion reached.

The Basic Problem

The corona virus, designated as SARS-CoV-2 or Covid-19 also called the "China Virus" due to its origin from Wuhan in China in 2019, is a highly infectious influenza type virus. It is also called 'novel corona virus', due to it being a new strain of corona virus for which most of the world had little or no previous immunity.

This is the basic problem. Had it been a type of virus which was close enough to previous influenza types, highly infectious or not, the fact that it spread to become a pandemic would not have caused much more disruption than normal influenzas which appear every winter; because some immunity in the nations of the world would have reduced the spread and the intensity of illness which ensued. [LLD + QLD = D]

Hence it is clear to the world that it is immunity which we need and the search for a vaccine is based on getting that immunity; a working vaccine would prime the human immune system such that the virus attack could be more easily beaten.

Hence this paper is centred on the efficacy of the immune system in elderly people, so that the underlying cause of the number of deaths can be properly understood. The process of joining up the dots will show that thousands of people every week in the UK are admitted to hospital with their health having been severely affected by errors in the medications prescribed by the NHS system; some of these errors will have seriously affected the immune system of the patients. These admissions are mainly due to a 999 emergency call due to a serious health situation; what we need to consider is that these admissions did not stop occurring during the covid-19 pandemic, but the patients were then going - as we say - "from the frying pan into the fire". Hence if their death was about to happen from a medication error of the NHS system, we need to ask, "Was the covid-19 pandemic situation either a good cover or a contributing factor in the death of the patient?"; albeit the doctors and nurses were not fully aware of their health situation.

The severity of any illness in any person is basically due the readiness of the patients immune system in the first hours and days of the infection invading the body. A slow, poor or weakened immune system gives the virus those vital hours of advantage in which to multiply in the patient's body and cause disruptions to the body's functions. Survival or death from covid-19 is strongly linked to the immune system's readiness.

Getting and Keeping a Good Immune System

As new born babies we all acquire a basic immune system from our mother. This will see us through the first six months of life. During that time our body replaces this primary system with its own bespoke system, as we become exposed to various moulds, viruses and bacteria. These three pathogens relate to the three basic elements of air, fire (or heat) and water respectively. Moulds live and transmit mainly through the air. Viruses prefer warm blooded creatures and pass from one to another through air and contact in other ways. Bacteria are mainly related to water for both their survival and transmission; they can manage well in cold conditions.

Since as children we are exposed to these three elements and their respective pathogens also through contact with other people, we get various illnesses and either die from one of them or develop immunity to them all. In many cases the immune system holds on to elements of the immunity which it creates and may continue to protect us from further infections of those illnesses which we have been exposed to. Hence as we get older we should gradually develop a better and better immune system within our bodies. Yet due to various external influences the immune system within our body can become weakened or damaged. This can happen at any age; it is not restricted to older people. If we had no immune system at all, death would be a certainty within days, because the immune system is constantly 24/7 fighting off the effects of invasions within our body from numerous pathogens of the three types mentioned above. So a weakened or damaged immune system means that the pathogen will begin to overwhelm the body, necessitating intervention from the medical profession. This overwhelming event can be sudden, as with influenza or very slow as with various types of cancer; and of course in-between these two.

Few people have any knowledge or understanding of their immune system. Hence they commonly, and unknowingly, abuse it by exposing it to damaging substances or foods etc. So now we need to look a little closer at how the human immune system is created and maintained; and how it can be damaged.

The Human Immune System

Surprisingly the immune system within the blood largely stems (70% to 80%) from the microbes which live within our small intestine, the intestinal flora. There is a symbiosis between the cells of the intestine and the cells of the large range of microbes which live in the human gut; called the intestinal flora. There are trillions of microbes in the intestine, some good and some not so good, with a combined genetic range more than 100 times that of our whole body. It is indeed one of nature's wonders and almost a miracle. Few people have understood that keeping the gut flora healthy will keep the whole body healthy by creating a vibrant immune system. In the European area of the Balkans this has been known for many centuries, perhaps by inference or trial and error. The peoples of that area daily consume a living bacteria called yoghurt; many people of that area live to be well over 100 years. This yoghurt bacteria may have been originally derived from the gut of goats. The bacteria live on milk and forms a thick white curd. It is now known that this live yoghurt will boost the health of the human intestinal flora by helping to eliminate bad bacteria and support good bacteria. Hence the longevity of the Balkans people. Old age does not automatically mean poor health, as long as the intestinal flora are cared for.

What are good gut bacteria? These are the ones which contribute to creating our immune system. They have to contend with the bad bacteria which come into the gut via the food we eat. The yoghurt bacteria help them with their battle. The gut is lined with a skin called the epithelial barrier. This does a job much like the skin outside of our body, and has the ability to prevent entry of harmful microbes into the blood stream. But the magic is that it also has the ability to allow beneficial chemistry and cells to pass through into the blood stream from the bacterial food mass in the intestine. This is the gut's contribution to the health of the immune system. The gut bacteria produce immune system chemistry. Knowledge of this gut immune system was not so well known before this 21st century.

The immune system is composed of an orchestra of different cell types. Each one plays its role in the battle to fight off the constant attack of pathogens which are trying to infect our body. For example the cells, now called CD8 T cells, kill thousands of virus infected cells in our body every day. The battle is constantly going on. The T cells of various types are vital to our survival. These T cells are an army which should be able to respond quickly to such a thing as the covid-19 virus infection.

Those researching cancer in the UK have discovered that if the human immune system is stimulated in the right way it will kill off cancer cells in the body. The cells known as B cells create and release anti-bodies to combat specific attacks by viruses in the body. Such is the power that Mother Nature has given us to combat disease.

There is much more to the complexity of the human immune system; but my point here is that it needs to be kept in tip-top condition; especially when we are likely to be exposed to a virus attack such as covid-19; and keeping the immune system in good condition is largely dependant on what we put into our mouths as food and drink etc.; including medicines and other such substances.

How Can the Immune System be Damaged

It has already been stated that introducing good bacteria by way of live bacteria yoghurt can boost the immune system. But if we consume other things which would kill or weaken the good bacteria in the gut, then eating live yoghurt would not be very effective. Such common things as alcohol and caffeine will damage the intestinal flora. Both these chemicals are poisons to the body's systems; there is no safe level of them despite what those who sell them say. Perhaps a single isolated introduction of these things will allow the good bacteria to recover. But constantly consuming such poisons will make their job more difficult. Thus reducing the chemistry process within the gut and passing less of that vital chemistry across the epithelial skin to assist the immune chemistry in the blood. In these modern times with a daily intake of the above two poisons combined with a junk food approach to diet, the immune system is weakened permanently. Hence people of all age ranges get more and more ailments.

Eating large amounts of red meat or other meat products will introduce more bad bacteria into the gut, hence potentially damaging the intestinal flora and the subsequent effect on the immune system. Some foods help; others can damage the system.

Another of the common substances which damage the gut flora are antibiotics. These are commonly prescribed and often in error for treatment of virus infections. As their name suggests, they are killers of microbes (poisons); so they will also kill good bacteria in the gut. In tests carried out in the USA (MIT, Harvard and the Wyss Institute) discovered that animals infected with E. Coli (a common harmful bacteria) had the cells of their immune system impeded by the effect of the antibiotics administered. But common sense will tell us, from what we have seen

above, that any poison put into the human body (imbibed or injected) will have an effect on the immune system [LLD + QLD = D]. Injection will damage the immune cells in the blood. By mouth it will damage the intestinal flora and impede or damage the immune system. Medicines do not discriminate between the pathogen they are attacking, the good microbes in the body or the vital cells of our immune system in the blood stream.

It is also clear that the use of other modern pharmaceuticals may also have a harmful effect on the bodies systems. In October 2019 the House of Lords in the UK debated the effect of taking too many modern medicines; in some cases more than five types of medicine. It was stated that a single modern drug would be tested on younger people, perhaps with one ailment only. The effect of the same dose on older people, who may have multiple ailments, is not known or tested. That same committee reported that nearly 7% of all hospital admissions in the UK had been due to adverse reactions from taking modern drugs (side effects). There are 6.5 million emergency admission annually in England (NHS data); 7% of this figure is 455,000 per year (37,916 per month). Here we have a clue as to how it can be that so many older people in the UK have suffered badly from the covid-19 infection [LLD + QLD = D]. Is the UK's NHS not such a good thing for older people where medications are concerned?

The US National Research Council have verified a long list of chemical substances which affect the production of T cells in immune systems. Most modern medicines are synthesised chemical substances. Many of these act as immuno-suppressants (poisons).

Medicines and the UK National Health System

Let us look at the catalogue of information on medicines and the UK's NHS which has appeared in the years prior to the advent of covid-19.

A study by the UK Universities of Manchester, Sheffield and York made headline news on 23rd Feb. 2018. It stated the following facts for the yearly figures in England UK.

"Mistakes with the prescribing, dispensing and/or administering of modern NHS medicines have killed 1,700 people and caused the subsequent deaths of a further 22,000 people (every year). 1 in 5 of all dispensations are in error which means 237 million prescriptions are dangerous, 79 million of these mistakes have caused harm to patients."

This is a damning indictment of the use of medications by the UK's NHS.

In the October 2019 House of Lords debate cited above, it was also stated that the GPs (medical practitioners) of the population were not fully informed on the effect of multiple medications on their patients. Multiple side effects can produce a worse state of health than the illnesses which they attempted to alleviate. During the debate Prof. Miles Witham, of the University of Newcastle stated :-

“Historically the NHS has been designed, or has evolved, to deal with single problems in single organ systems, and has evolved really to deal with episodic care,” he also said. “It is less good and less well designed at dealing with chronic care and it is particularly poorly equipped to deal with multiple problems affecting a single person.”

Also at the same debate Sir Munir Pirmohamed, the professor of molecular and clinical pharmacology at Liverpool University, said that most of his patients are on more than 10 and often more than 20 drugs. Also he said :-

“Those drugs are used at conventional doses and those doses have been tested in younger populations who had exclusion criteria for trials – so they have been tested in people who don’t have the multiple diseases. So when we use a drug at a dose which is licensed at the moment, we are often ‘poisoning’ the elderly because of the dosing that we are using.”

This poisoning would also be poison for the bacteria in the gut.

[LLD + QLD = D] .

In August 2019 the charity Age UK in their report called "More Harm Than Good", recommended to the UK government that older people who were taking numerous medicines should have their situation reviewed so as to try and reduce the number of medications they were taking. Their research stated that nearly 2 million older people were taking 7 or more prescription medications daily, or more than 4 million taking 5 or less per day; and that they were at risk of severe side effects (this number is more than 50% of the over 60s population of the UK). Older person's health was being seriously affected by the combined effect of too many medications. In some cases death had resulted directly from the side effects of too many medicines; some of which were not really needed or were over-prescribed. In the above Age UK report it was stated :-

"Adverse drug reactions can have severe consequences for older people and cause nearly 6 percent of unplanned hospital admissions.

Between 2008 and 2015 the number of emergency hospital admissions caused by adverse drug reactions increased by 53 percent. In 1 in 50 cases that reaction proved to be fatal."

[from above - subsequent deaths of a further 22,000 people. (every year)]

So the University study in 2018 cited above of 23,700 deaths every year is not a myth. The UK's NHS is killing those people it supposed to be curing. This is unacceptable.

Further to the above, in January 2020 the BBC made a "Freedom of Information Request" about the compensation paid out by the NHS in 2019.

The figures showed that the NHS was in debt for about £4,000,000,000 (four billion pounds sterling) of legal fees. But it also showed that the NHS had paid out £83,000,000,000 (83 billion pounds sterling) in compensation claims for negligence (medical mistakes).

Although not commented on by the BBC, this shows that the UK government was hiding a dark and serious secret, otherwise a freedom of information request would not have been necessary. How many of those claims relate to medication errors? Maybe hundreds of thousands.

From the above we can see that the once time applauded NHS was clearly in crisis over many issues. Poor control of treatment and where the elderly were concerned their health was being made worse due to over medication. In 2017 NHS medical researchers into the over-prescription of drugs stated that people in the UK were :-

"Moving from the kingdom of the well into the kingdom of the sick."

Due to the use of more medicines to counter side effects; which may eventually damage the immune system.

Are we now getting closer to understanding how many older people in the UK were disproportionately affected by the corona-19 virus infection? If their immune systems were being damaged, they stood less chance of fighting the virus than they would have done with a fully functioning immune system, as in those who do not take medications. Not simply because they were older. Also if they were already suffering weakness or sickness due to multiple side effects of medication, how could their bodies have the strength to deal with the corona virus infection? [LLD + QLD = D] This is the answer to my question above, "*Is the UK's NHS not such a good thing for older people?*"

Don't misunderstand the above focus on failures. There is no attempt here to undermine the heroic efforts made by front line staff in the covid-

19 epidemic in the UK; the nurses and the doctors. There is no doubt that they have done a first class job in treating all the patients who have come to them with the infection. But the question should be asked, "How many of the older patients who have suffered so badly could have dealt with the infection at home, if their general health and their immune system had not been previously compromised by the same NHS which was subsequently trying to save their lives?" Because the evidence is clear - we need an immune system in tip top condition to fight off a virus attack on our body's systems; also we know that modern medications are poisoning the patients and are damaging the immune system.

Breaking News :- On the 13th June 2020 Medscape published on the internet news taken from the British Medical Journal, the main points being :-

"More than 237 million medication errors are made all along the care process every year in England alone, estimated to cost the NHS at least UK£98 million and contributing to the loss of more than 1,700 lives annually, say UK researchers. "

"Rachel Ann Elliott, PhD, professor in health economics, Manchester Centre for Health Economics, University of Manchester, and colleagues used a range of sources to examine the adverse drug event (ADE) rate in primary and secondary care, and in care homes."

"---25% of errors having the potential to cause moderate harm and only 2% potentially resulting in serious harm."

This shows us many things. Firstly that the findings of the Universities of Manchester, Sheffield and York in 2017 published in early 2018 (mentioned above), have not been addressed by the UK's NHS system with any success. And because the researchers did not address every aspect of such a serious catalogue of mistakes, we need to ask the following important questions:-

- 1. How does a medication, supposed to cure, kill a patient?**
- 2. Are the medications poisonous or potentially lethal?**
- 3. Did the medical mistakes damage the immune system of the patients?**
- 4. Has the UK's NHS become broken with regard to medications?**
- 5. How many patients did not die but were made seriously ill?**
- 6. Has anyone responsible for these mistakes been prosecuted?**

No doubt some of the answers to these questions will never be found. However, it seems the answer to (b) is certainly "yes" since 1,700 people did die. The answer to (c) is almost certainly yes. The answer to (e) is

possible to derive from the figures. Death can be included in the term "serious harm" without any risk of error; and 2% of 237 million equates to 4,740,000 medicine errors yearly, which have caused serious harm. Take away the 1,700 deaths and we get 4,738,300 cases each year of serious harm. As it looks like this is an annual recurrence (i.e. at least from the evidence above in 2018 giving us the clue) then there are 394,858 cases of serious harm to patients every month of the year on average. If we say that the same patient may be involved in three cases of error per year (this is a guess), then we have 1/3rd or 131,619 different people suffering serious harm each month.

At the time of writing this paper the pandemic in the UK has been killing people since March 10th; this is three months. In those three months we would have 394,858 people suffering serious harm from NHS medicine errors. During that time there have been 41,700 deaths attributed to covid-19. It is very clear that the deaths occurring in the UK hospitals are not due to people contracting covid-19 alone. They have got the virus, but because they are some of the ones who were suffering serious harm due to medicine errors supplied by the UK NHS system, they have died because their strength to resist illness and their immune system were both seriously compromised due to medication errors.

It was stated many times during the height of the covid-19 infections, that the majority of those who died from the covid-19 infection had previous underlying health conditions. This infers that they would have been on multiple NHS medications with all the effects on their health discussed above; perhaps they were also actually ill from over medication or medication errors. Although this information cannot be given publically by the hospitals due to what is called "patient confidentiality". Under the banner of patient confidentiality the NHS is able to hide many cases of medical mistakes and failures; or factors which have influenced death of their patients. Simply because all the facts cannot be legally divulged. All causes of deaths in the UK have to be certified by a qualified medical practitioner. The easiest issuing of death certificates comes through the UK hospital route. Fewer questions are asked if a person was old and had been admitted to hospital as a person needing emergency health treatment; also inquests are rare. If an older patient tests positive for covid-19 then it is easy to put that on the death certificate; even though the patient may have been suffering from severe side effects of multiple medications. Or may have had a compromised immune system unknown to the doctors. Here it is clear

that the emergency hospital admissions due to medication errors were mixed in with covid-19 cases.

Is Age a Factor?

At the beginning of the lock-down for the covid-19 strategy in the UK, the government stated that people over 65 years of age were vulnerable and should not go out. Their supplies of food should be brought to them by a relative, friend or a neighbour. As the lock-down progressed the term elderly was continued to be used to warn those over 65 that they should take more precautions.

Gradually evidence around the world showed that very old people were beating off the virus attack after being hospitalised. A 90 year old woman in Seattle USA; in India a 93 year old man survived the virus; in March 2020 a 94 year old woman in the UK survived after struggling for nine days in hospital; in the same month a 95 year old grandmother survive the virus in Italy; later two others in Italy survived, a 101 year old man and a 102 year old woman. On 12th May the news was announced from Spain that the world's oldest woman at 113 years of age had survived contracting covid-19. There are many more examples of over 90s surviving covid-19. So it became clear that the human immune system does not get weaker as we get older - providing of course that we look after it in the manner described above. Nothing of the life style was mentioned about the above older survivors. But we can be sure that to have reached an age of around 90 or older and be healthy, the life style of those survivors was most likely not like those of the modern age - alcohol, too much coffee, junk food and the need to take multiple medicines.

Not surprisingly the UK government in May 2020 stopped mentioning "older people" in the various bits of advice which came out. As the lock-down began to be lifted near the end of May, no mention was made in the advice, for older people or people over 65 as being restricted or being vulnerable. When it was allowed for people to go out of the home to visit places, no mention was made that over 65s should not go out or should take greater precautions. So by saying nothing it seems that the over 65s had magically become more resistant to the virus than at the start of the epidemic in the UK. But the truth is that the UK government's original advice for over 65s was based on those who had been rushed into hospital and had tested positive for covid-19. It was often appended to the announcement of the deaths that underlying health conditions were the contributing cause. Most of them had died.

But from the evidence presented above we can see clearly that the reason they died may not have been the covid-19 virus alone, nor the underlying health conditions. It is almost certain that those older people already had a compromised immune system which had caused them to become hospitalised in the first place; caused by over-prescription of medications combined with the unhealthy food and drink approach mentioned above. An immune system in tip top condition is at the centre of our survival; it is mainly the things we put into our mouths which prevent this.

Some years back, my wife's friend (in her 70s) started to have hallucinations, so she went to see her doctor. By luck her normal doctor was not at the surgery, she was seen by a lady doctor. This doctor asked about the medications the patient was taking. She told the doctor of the list of about 6 or 7 different pills each day. The doctor said that she should stop taking all the pills for two weeks and come back for another consultation. After two weeks all her previous symptoms, including the hallucinations, had disappeared. She is now a much healthier person.

My wife runs a cinema club at the local college. They are all well over 65. She has heard of more than one who has contracted covid-19 and survived at home. I am the chairman of the City of London's Pensioners' Association. We have more than 1,250 members. We keep in touch with all members through a network of volunteer local representatives. We have heard of only one who has passed away from covid-19. So the answer to the question, "Is age a factor?" is strongly veering towards "No!"

What we in the UK need to be honest about or to realise, is that the UK has one of the worlds highest rates of use of modern pharmaceuticals; and this especially in the older generation; coupled as we have seen with a high rate of errors in administering those medicines. In the UK most general practitioners (GPs) are so overworked that patients get less than 10 minutes for a consultation during their visit to the surgery. The easiest thing for GPs so as to send the patient away with a solution, is to prescribe a modern medicine. In the Age UK report "More Harm than Good" it was stated that GPs are :-

"-- over-stretched and in a hurry so prescribing a drug is a quick and easy thing for them to do to help an older person, whereas if they had longer they might decide another approach would be safer and more effective."

And as we have seen above many GPs are not trained in, neither are they aware of, the combined effect of multiple medications on the elderly. Fortunately for my wife's friend she saw a doctor who had taken the trouble to research the effect of multiple medications. What often happens is that a side effect of one drug is taken to be a new sickness and is treated with another drug; and so the process goes on until patients are taking multiple medications. We should also be honest and realise that the term "side effect" is a polite term for another symptom or another illness. No patient will accept a medicine if they are told that it will likely give them another illness; hence the crafty use of the term "side effect". This way 'big pharmas' get away with murder.

So "age" is surely a factor in reduced survival of the covid-19 virus; but only if the term "the elderly" is taken to mean or to assume that, as Sir Munir Pirmohamed said above,

"Most of my patients are on more than 10 and often more than 20 drugs."

Research was done by Oxford University for the British Geriatrics Society, into the multiple medication use in the older UK population. They produced their findings in March 2018. Their result showed the following :-

"Medication use, including both prescribed medicines and over the counter products has increased dramatically over the last 2 decades. The number of people taking five or more items quadrupled from 12% to 49%, while the proportion of people who did not take any medication has decreased from around 1 in 5 to 1 in 13."

In a report in the Guardian newspaper on 30th August 2018, where over prescription of medicines in the UK was discussed, Aseem Malhotra stated:-

"The consequences have been devastating. Modern medicine, through over prescription, represents a major threat to public health. Peter Gøtzsche, co-founder of the reputed Cochrane Collaboration, estimates that prescribed medication is the third most common cause of death globally after heart disease and cancer. In the UK, use of prescription drugs is at an all-time high, with almost half of adults on at least one drug and a quarter on at least three – an increase of 47% in the past decade. It's instructive to note that life expectancy in the UK has stalled since 2010, the slowdown being one of the most significant in the world's leading economies."

Is the UK's NHS killing more people than it saves? Will we ever know?

The UK has now one of the unhealthiest older populations in the world - not due to old age, but mainly due to the medications which were originally supposed to make us well. This is the real cause behind why so many older people in the UK have died from contracting covid-19. [LLD + QLD = D] Not because they are old per se. They have been wrongly prescribed medications; they have had a severe reaction to these medications this may have coincided with contracting covid-19 hence they needed to call 999. Having been weakened by the drug reaction and their immune system affected by the medications they stood very little chance of surviving the covid-19 infection.

How have we in the UK allowed this to happen? The answer is in the secretive way that health matters are dealt with in the UK. I mentioned "patient confidentiality" above; but there is much more. How can we change a situation if we are not open and honest about it and are not in possession of all relevant information.

Keeping Secrets

Many western style countries often accuse countries like Russia, Iran and China of not being honest with their people. They keep many facts secret from the population at large. This they do so as to enable their leaders to maintain control of their people. Here in the UK the government is not innocent of the same charge. But maybe the reasons are different. We have already seen above that the BBC had to issue a "Freedom of Information" request so as to find out the data on the financial status of the UK's NHS system. The information they obtained was not in the public domain.

The dark and serious secret mentioned above was the fact that the UK's NHS was at the point of financial collapse early in 2020. This had not been publically announced nor admitted in any way. Yet many people in the UK were beginning to become aware that this was the true situation. In numerous hospitals many systems were already overwhelmed; many hospitals had little spare capacity. Waiting lists for treatment were getting longer and longer. [LLD + QLD = D]

Hence it was no surprise to some people that the lock-down mantra used by the UK government stated; "Stay at home, **save the NHS** and save lives." The government knew that the highly infectious nature of the new covid virus would cause all beds to become filled and people in need would be refused hospitalisation in large numbers. This situation

they deemed collapse of the NHS. This would have been a national scandal, with the potential to bring down any UK government. This was the main reason for the lock down of the whole economy and the government's agreement to spend many billions on supporting the economy (save the NHS). Collapse of the NHS would bring their secrets out into the open. For political reasons it was vital to keep this under wraps. Had the government spent those billions in previous years on the NHS, the total lock-down could have been avoided. Many countries have avoided a total lock-down and have survived it.

But the UK government had at the same time been made aware of four things;

- (1) the poor state of the health of many older people due to over medication and
- (2) the financial crisis in the NHS.
- (3) The NHS can expect nearly 38,000 emergency cases of severe health problems due to medication errors arriving at UK hospitals every month.
- (4) The highly infectious nature of the covid-19 virus will also bring many thousands of cases to the hospital system and the NHS system will likely collapse.

All of these would be brought to light when the covid-19 virus accelerated its hold on the British people. [LLD + QLD = D] The government are comfortably blaming the covid-19 virus for the huge number of deaths, especially of the elderly. But as this paper shows - the virus is not the main factor here. The previous health of the patients and their immune system is the main factor. But there are other mistakes as well. The following could not be kept secret.

Prior to the covid-19 epidemic in the UK a large number of hospital beds were taken up by older people waiting for social care in the community. This situation had arisen due to insufficient funding for the social care available within each local authority; another health system in crisis. This situation was known as "bed blocking" it was generally elderly patients. The hospitals had done all they could for the patient, but they were not well enough to go back to their own home where sufficient after care would not be available; hence they are kept in a hospital bed.

In early April 2020 the covid-19 epidemic began to produce large numbers of infected people requiring hospitalisation. The UK government issued guidance that care homes should play their part in helping to clear hospital beds for covid-19 patients who needed them. They were

pressured into taking bed blocking patients from hospitals. But due to the lack of protective clothing in hospitals for nurses and doctors, the covid-19 virus had unknowingly spread to many of the "bed blocking" elderly people. When they were farmed out to care homes they spread the infection to those residents already there. The result was that nearly 7,000 older people in care homes have so far died of covid-19. We can understand that many of those, both "bed blocking" patients and care home residents would likely be taking 5 to 10 medications per day. Hence they had compromised immune systems. But their original reason for care was not covid-19 related. Hence we can say that they were put at risk of death due to an NHS and government blunder.

Conclusions

At the time of preparing this paper nearly 42,000 deaths had occurred due to covid-19 in the UK NHS system. Around 82% of these were what was termed "elderly" which probably means over 60 years. The over 60s in the UK comprise 18% of the population. This means the disproportionate ratio in the elderly is more than 4.0 for deaths due to covid-19. This cannot be explained nor proved that their age was the main factor in the increase in deaths of the elderly. [LLD + QLD = D] There is evidence arising from blood tests which is showing that those who died had a severely reduced number of immune system T cells in their blood. The researchers are blaming the covid-19 virus for causing this reduction. But as this paper shows, the most likely cause is a catalogue of poor diet, poor health and a compromised immune system from too many medications or from medication errors. Meaning that they arrived into hospital with a reduced number of T cells from the start and a weakened state of health due to medication errors.

Yes it is true that older people in the UK are more at risk from death due to covid-19. But this must be qualified by saying that any person in any age group who has a pre-existing health problem and may be taking a number of NHS medications, that they are at an equal risk to those elderly people who have a similar situation. Any older person who is fit, does not take multiple NHS medications, has a balanced and healthy diet with a correspondingly healthy life style, would be at no more risk of a sever illness from covid-19 than any other person. The survival of so many over 90s is proof of this.

I have taken information from a wide range of sources to open up this topic. I am not a health professional, but I have since my early teens been deeply interested in human physiology and all matters connected

with health. I hope that the information put together here would open a new debate into the use of modern pharmaceuticals. This is not the purpose of the paper, but a possible beneficial "side effect".

But the evidence is clear :-

- (a) Older people are taking more medications than they need to take, as detailed in the Age UK document "More Harm Than Good." See page 5.
- (b) Many medications are damaging to the human immune system. See page 4.
- (c) Medications are being dispensed in error and are making many older people suffer serious health conditions; according to health researchers at the Universities of Manchester, Sheffield and York; see reports on pages 5 and 6.
- (d) Approximately 131,619 cases of serious harm due to medication errors are coming to UK hospitals every month (more than 4,000 every day) see page 7.
- (e) Older people suffering impaired immune systems and weak from the serious harm due to medication errors, infected with covid-19 virus, do not stand much chance of survival.
- (f) Finally, from the above, we can say that it is not the covid-19 virus which is responsible for the high number of older people who have died from the infection.

Yes it is true that it is a highly infectious virus, also it is a new virus in that very few people have any previous exposure to it. Hence the world has suffered from a high number of cases and a rapid spread of the disease. But if the so called advanced nation of the UK has a medication problem as described above, how many other countries in the world have a similar situation with sick people and damaged immune systems. The large number of deaths is likely to be due to the poor health situation of the people more than the virus. The human immune system, working well, is capable of dealing with any new virus and to successfully combat it. If this were not the case, there would not be a human race on this planet.

Addendum One

Why are UK Health Professionals Intent on Using Modern Drugs

A brief survey of other countries in Europe and indeed the USA shows that many natural products are used to treat patients across a wide range of ailments. In 2014 the European Medicines Agency approved the use of 622 herbal medicines across all member states; the

second highest use was for respiratory ailments (colds and influenza). The American Journal of Medicine reports that 25% of people in the USA use herbal medicines from a range of 20,000 products.

What do I mean by natural products? These are plant extracts and other plant medicines taken from the leaves, fruits, flowers, seeds, stems or roots of plants and the bark of trees. For many thousands of years such cures have been used. This time span is itself sufficient evidence that such remedies work well, else they could not have been continuously applied within human communities. Modern 'big pharmas' try to short cut the impressive track record of herbal cures, using what they call "clinical trials" which may only span a few years, not centuries. Herbal cures usually have very few side effects, yet they are powerful and must be used with caution, since they can be harmful if taken in excess. But it is unknown that any herbal remedy has damaged the immune system of human beings. On the contrary many herbal medicines will boost or enhance the immune system. This is the important fact for the main purpose of this paper.

The UK government is exceptional in an almost outright refusal to officially accept herbal remedies, especially in the NHS system. This is not 100% within the medical profession in the UK. In the past century many GPs recommended and supported the use natural cures. But as the decades have passed in the last century, there has been less and less use of them in the UK national official medical profession. This is also connected with the UK's NHS; which was created after the second world war in the 1940s. For older people medicines are now provided free through the prescription system. The GP decides which drug to administer and issues a prescription. This document is taken to the pharmacist and providing the declaration on the form claiming exemption from payment is completed, there will be nothing to pay. As far as I know there are no natural cures available through this prescription system; only modern drugs.

In 1972 I was diagnosed with a bad case of haemorrhoids (piles). The GP referred me to the local NHS hospital for examination. The situation was so extraordinary the consultant at the hospital asked my permission for a group of student trainee consultants to be allowed to watch the video as the camera went through the various right angle bends of my colon. The discussion which took place then allowed me to know the severity of my case. The consultant recommended surgery to cut out the offending veins from my colon. Treating the symptom but not the cause. I agreed to have an appointment for the operation. During the waiting

period I went to a herbalist who did his own diagnosis of the situation. He said that the cause was a blockage in the portal vein due to my liver having slight sclerosis. He proposed a two stage treatment : (1) to treat the cause by curing the sclerosis and clearing the blockage using a herbal tincture; (2) treating the symptom of stretched veins by the use of other herbal medicine to shrink the veins back to their normal size. I accepted the treatment. Within less than one month he examined me again and stated that the problem was resolved. I forgot about the hospital operation. Two months later I was contacted by the hospital to prepare for the surgery to remove the veins from my colon. I contacted the consultant and told him that the problem had gone away and seemed OK. He made an appointment for me to have another consultation. After he examined me with the internal camera he agreed that the problem was no more. This was absolute proof to me that the herbal method had worked. The piles have never come back. This was the first time I had been to a herbalist. It changed my view of things.

Since that time I have taken a closer interest in natural cures. A herbalist had successfully treated me such that I had avoided having potentially devastating surgery to my colon. This to me seemed like magic at that time. Later other successes with herbal cures are :-(1) my wife had recurring cystitis since her teenage years. All modern medical treatments failed to help with it. One visit to the same herbalist who treated my piles cured her for ever of cystitis. After 40 years it has never returned. (2) During my wife's pregnancy of our first child the hospital diagnosed severe anaemia. Her blood iron count was dangerously low and the child foetus was at risk. She told me that she had always been anaemic since childhood. Several remedies from the UK NHS were administered. None of them increased her blood count sufficiently. On a visit to the same herbalist he gave a months supply of capsules. After taking them her blood count was normal at the next NHS test. My wife had two more children since that time - she has never had anaemia again even to the present time; our first child is 49 years old this year. Finally (3) in 2006 during a regular health check-up my PSA (prostate specific antigen) was normal at 1.61. PSA is a cancer indicator. The estimated weight of the prostate was about 40 grams. This remained about the same in 2007 through to 2013. In 2015 the PSA was 3.33 and the prostate was estimated at 85 grams; a sudden doubling of the numbers. I was told that this indicated cancer of the prostate. I immediately sought herbal remedies. Administering both turmeric and taheebo (or Pau d'Arco) for several months remedied the situation. A further check on

the numbers showed PSA at 2.65 and the prostate at 61 grams. The signs of cancer have gone away. Once again absolute proof that natural cures do work.

There are many other personal and family successes with natural cures which I could site here. But the main point is that herbal remedies do work for the wide range of common health problems. So back to the question at the top, "Why UK GPs insist on modern drugs?"

All GPs in the UK are required to keep up to date with new developments in the medical field. This includes knowledge of new medicines etc. This process is the same for many professionals in the UK, it is called "continuing professional development" or CPD. There are a wide range of CPD courses (seminars) which GPs can attend. Many are also online courses which are more convenient for most busy GPs, as they can do them from the comfort of their homes. One of the largest contributors to the online CPD courses on medicines come naturally from those companies who produce those medicines; the giant pharmaceutical companies. Many of whom are global companies and some of the richest in the world. There is fierce competition between these companies. Any particular human ailment may have hundreds of medicines (modern drugs) which are supposed to cure the symptoms or alleviate the condition. It is clear from the text above that such companies are more interested in getting their own drugs accepted on the market than they are in curing illness or saving lives. Why you may ask? Simply because all modern drugs are hurriedly put onto the market after only a few years of clinical trials (naturally they cannot wait for decades). Also all modern drugs have side effects (another symptom or illness) and cause harm to patients and in many cases death (see above evidence of this).

Not one medical herbalist would use a natural cure in such a dosage which had the possibility of causing harm in any way to their patients. Most medical herbalists make their own medicines from plants which they know are the ones they need. This means they are personally responsible for the outcome of administering the medicine. In the UK the system of GPs avoids this personal responsibility in two ways:-

(1) the GPs are in practise groups and have a group insurance which means the practice will take the blame. (2) The GPs do not make the medicines and are not involved in the trials to test their efficacy, hence they are not so knowledgeable of the possible side effects. This is the responsibility of the company which buy the production license from the pharmaceutical companies ('big pharma') which develop the medicines;

or the 'big pharma' themselves if they produce the medicines they have developed.

So back to the CPD courses. There is no doubt that wherever a 'big pharma' provides a CPD course, they are primarily interested in promoting their own products; this is evident because many such CPD courses are produced within the marketing section of the 'big pharma's'. This means there is considerable pressure put onto GPs to use modern pharmaceuticals. In a report of the British Pharmaceutical Industry on CPD for GPs it is stated:-

"Opponents of industry sponsorship of doctors' CPD argue that there is an inevitable conflict of interest, and that activities are undertaken purely to promote the sales of a company's own products. The heavy investment by pharmaceutical companies may also discourage doctors from considering non-pharmaceutical interventions. Alternative models could be envisaged in which CPD is financed directly by doctors, through their employer, the NHS, or through an independent body funded by industry. In the USA, for example, the pharmaceutical industry cannot contribute directly to continuing medical education."

The term "non-pharmaceutical interventions" above actually means the use of natural cures. There are no CPD courses on natural medicines. Hence we can see how easy it is for a GP to simply recommend a modern drug because

- (a) there is no direct responsibility for the side effects; the producer of the medicine is supposed to make the patient aware of side effects within the packaging of the medicine.
- (b) GPs only have education based on the use of modern drugs, hence they are not made aware of natural cures.
- (c) Modern drugs are the only ones supported for dispensation, so the GP cannot prescribe a natural cure.

Here I have highlighted the situation in the UK with the use of modern drugs. Across the world countries are using natural cures which do not damage the human immune system. The UK is stuck in the dark ages from the time when the ladies who knew about natural medicines were called witches by the religious people. Many hundreds of thousands of these community doctors were burnt tied to a wooden stake. This burnt into some facets of the UK establishment that natural cures were suspect and should never be trusted. The 21st century understanding of natural cures is the opposite of this.

It is quite clear that the UK NHS has gone off the rails with regard to the administration of medications. What is really needed is a return to natural medications which do not kill patients. Modern medications may claim to derive their chemistry from naturally occurring plants and other substances, but the fact is they are mostly synthesised chemistry. Chemists really believe that they can analyse any plant extract which has been found to heal, and hence to understand the chemical make up of the substance. They really believe that they can replicate this chemistry in large amounts for commercial purposes. It is these beliefs which have infected 'big pharma' and the health authorities. When I say 'infected' I mean they have a misplaced faith that these claims are irrefutable. The evidence we have is contrary to this belief, simply because it has been shown above that modern medications kill the patients. [LLD + QLD = D] i.e. they are poisons.

It is true that in the 19th century in the UK there were many false doctors who would advertise wonder cures and dupe unsuspecting public by their concoctions. Many of these were bogus claims and some resulted in harm to patients. They were not interested in the health of the public but only in getting their money. These false doctors were given the name "quacks".

- (1) They gave medications which were supposed to cure people.
- (2) In many cases the medicines caused harm to their patients.
- (3) They were mainly interested in the money.

Eventually their medicines were banned or exposed as being false.

In the UK publication "The Week" 13th June 2020 a small article was published called "Big Pharma takes but doesn't give". It related to the search for a vaccine to help with the covid-19 pandemic. There it stated,

"Medicines are a human necessity, not a profit making machine."

It also pointed out how much public money (billions of UK£ sterling) had been given to 'big pharma' to help with finding a vaccine for covid-19. "Yet despite these huge subsidies, drug firms still charge what they want for the final product."

Being as we now know that many of the products from 'big pharma' actually kill people and hence do not cure them, we need to ask are 'big pharmas' the 21st century "Quacks"?

- (1) They give medications which are supposed to cure people.
- (2) In many cases the medicines caused harm to their patients.
- (3) They were mainly interested in the money.

If it looks like a duck and quacks like a duck then it is probably a duck. Quack! Quack!

Maybe now readers will come to understand some of the real reasons why so many more older people in the UK have died from covid-19 virus infection; and why it is that the UK, a modern developed nation, has one of the highest rates per million of its population who have died through infection with covid-19.

If the UK is to avoid a repeat of this appalling situation then there must be a complete review of medicines and their administration to the population. This should also include natural cures being used wherever they have been proved efficacious; so that the immune systems of the people generally can be best prepared for the next pandemic; which is likely in only a few years time.

Addendum Two- June 2020

Madagascar

See also Addendum Four April 2021 update related to the South African variant of covid 19.

There has been much written about the different countries in the world and the way they have met the challenge of the new influenza virus covid-19. But due to the World Health Organisation (WHO) being dominated by modern European or western style of medications discussed above (i.e. modern pharmaceuticals) most countries have ignored Madagascar's announcement of using an established herbal remedy for the sickness. During April 2020 the president of Madagascar, Andry Rajoelina, announced that the country was using an extract from the plant *artemisia annua* (also known as sweet worm-wood) to combat covid-19 infection. Soon after that several African countries expressed interest in using it. A senior medical scientist in Madagascar was questioned on television about whether clinical trials would be undertaken, she answered, "This medicine is an ancient Chinese remedy which we have used successfully for centuries. We used it to cure people of the previous SARS-Cov outbreak in 2002. So as far as we are concerned it does not need clinical trials". They are also using it as a preventative to covid-19; i.e. to boost the immune system of their population. Artemisinin has been shown to increase the number of the vital T cells in the immune system.

Extracts (*artemisinin*) from this plant have been used successfully to combat malaria of all three main types. Whereas modern drugs can only deal with one specific type of malaria. However the general western

approach, which is mainly prescribed by the Europeanised nations who fund WHO, means that it will not be accepted internationally until lengthy clinical trials on humans have been carried out and verified. Herbal remedies can be made by almost anyone and there are few if any intellectual production rights associated with them. Hence there is not a great fortune to be made in marketing them around the world as with the modern drugs, which make great sums of money for 'big pharmas' out of other people's health problems. This is the main reason behind 'big pharmas' using volumes of propaganda against herbal remedies; and another reason why UK GPs are being discouraged from recommending them. Most herbal practitioners do not practice their art to make a fortune, but to make effective cures available to all people at reasonable cost. However, researchers in Germany and Denmark are collaborating to test artemisinin extracts to discover whether it will be effective against covid-19.

But, I am sorry to say this, we cannot leave out the possibility that there is an underlying psychology within the European researchers, that those who are claiming to have a herbal remedy for covid-19 are not white skinned European types. Albeit that those who will evaluate the herb are not aware of their prejudice.

The herb comfrey is banned in the UK for internal use because trials on rats showed the possibility of some liver damage. Over many centuries there has been no evidence of liver damage in humans from comfrey. On the basis of that slight and doubtful probability with comfrey most modern medicines should also be banned.

Bartram's herbal encyclopaedia has the following entry with regard to the UK ban on comfrey.

"There is a growing body of opinion to support the belief that a herb which has, without ill-effects, been used for centuries and capable of producing convincing results is to be recognised as safe and effective."

The same could be said about the use of the artemisia for covid-19.

Also with the great expense and the large number of highly paid scientists, with all their highly complex equipment, and still not being able to find a vaccine or a cure for covid-19 (June 2020), the mindset of those involved is incapable of believing that an almost unheard of country and a simple plant remedy can have found the answer so easily. They will almost certainly find a slight possibility of damage to humans

so as to disqualify the artemisia remedy; or the tests will be declared “inconclusive”.

All this western sluggish and biased approach is costing lives. Not only the test of time, which supports herbal cures, but the actual numbers related to Madagascar should be evidence that there is substance in their statements about the effectiveness of artemisia annua, as being both a preventative and a cure. They have a population of around 26 million (UK is 67 million) ; and so far (on 15/06/2020) there have been 1,272 cases of covid-19 and 10 deaths in Madagascar, starting from about one week later than the UK (UK cases are about 298,000 and UK deaths are 41,500). For countries with populations over 25 million Madagascar's numbers are amongst the lowest in the world. Equating to 0.4 persons per million for deaths against the UK's 611 per million (a factor of 1,525). Even if Madagascar's numbers are under-reported by a factor of 10 (which I doubt very much) the UK, one of the most advanced nations in the world, still has 152 times as many deaths as Madagascar, per million of population.

On 20th April 2020 the president of Madagascar Rajoelina announced that, a 'remedy' based on the plant artemisia, which he had put forward 10 days earlier as a potential treatment, had passed tests (presumably on patients). He said, "Today, I officially announce the success and good results from the tests of our remedy." He also said, "We can say that it provides a conclusive result for covid-19 patients in Madagascar and can mitigate the impact on the human body." From that date Madagascar started to reduce the restrictions imposed by their lock-down. At that date there had been no deaths due to covid-19. Since that date there have been 10 deaths reported. Also the total number of cases at the time of writing this paper are 1,272. This situation is itself proof of what president Rajoelina has said in relation to the effect of the artemisia natural medication.

In contrast to Madagascar the UK has recommended the use of dexamethazone for treating severely affected covid-19 patients. The UK National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) lists the following conditions as common or very common side-effects of dexamethazone.

"Anxiety; cataract subcapsular; cognitive impairment; electrolyte imbalance; fatigue; fluid retention; gastrointestinal discomfort; headache; hypertension; increased risk of infection; nausea; osteoporosis; peptic ulcer; psychotic disorder; skin reactions; sleep

disorders; etc. and a number of others. It also suppresses the immune response in humans."

More uncommon side-effects include increased appetite, eye disorders, heart failure, seizure, tuberculosis reactivation and vertigo.

Comparing these to the slight and doubtful risk of liver damage from comfrey, such drugs as dexamethazone should never be allowed to be used. Now readers can see the prejudice which exists against the use of natural medicines in the UK. Most modern drugs used in the UK have equally as long and as severe a list of side effects as dexamethazone.

Before the next pandemic we must make sure the UK population has been weaned off excessive use of modern drugs and are encouraged to boost their immune system with healthy diets and the use of natural medicinal extracts. The high number of both hospitalised cases and deaths in the UK are mainly due to the unhealthy condition of the population in general caused by a poor life-style and medication errors. We should refrain from putting all the blame onto an influenza virus, which it has been proved beyond doubt that healthy human beings can deal with and only get mild symptoms. There needs to be a major rethink about medications of all types and the dangers and benefits of each.

Addendum Three (December 2020)

How Have we Become so Ignorant of Plant Medicines?

I quote here from a book published in the USA more than 50 years ago. It is about the use of indigenous medicines of the north american continent; some of which had been used for thousands of years before the Europeans invaded that country (colonised). My clarifying comments are in brackets. What is remarkable here is that this was written by a person who was of European stock. A rare example of liberated thinking.

"For a long time our ethnic (European) arrogance foreclosed any serious attention to the medical knowledge which the 'savages' might have. Our ancestors (British forefathers) were repelled by the 'superstitious rites' (non-Christian approach) which often accompanied the native curing procedures, and shrank from the notion that an 'uncivilised' race might have something to teach them. Consequently, 'Indian medicine' (american indigenous) long remained the last resort of the explorer and frontiersman (foreign invaders) and was later the adopted child of 'folk medicine' (officially unapproved). " (American Indian Medicine ISBN 0 8061 0863 0)

The Current Situation

It is clear during the covid 19 pandemic that Western thinking has not progressed any further than the view quoted above. Western arrogance is ruining economies and killing many thousands of people. It is now time for the West to wake up from slumber.

The table below is self explanatory in respect of the current statistics (12/11/2020) for various countries compared to the UK. All those on the table, other than the UK and Madagascar, had shown interest in the Madagascan claim for artemisia annua in April this year; and had placed orders for the purchase of the remedy from Madagascar. However, since the W.H.O. and other eminent scientists and medical people had downplayed the Madagascan remedy, most of those countries have kept quiet about what they are doing to help their populations deal with covid 19 infections. The results after more than six months of the pandemic are self explanatory. These results are on millions of covid 19 patients; not the few thousand people; which is the number used for modern clinical trials.

Some people have said that the low incidence of deaths in African countries is due to their high proportion of younger people in their populations. But my original concern was for the effect on the elderly within the UK. Hence I have also shown the proportion of each population where over 60s are concerned. This shows that the use of artemisia annua has still provided a huge benefit to those countries which may have used it.

Country	Total cases	Total deaths	Deaths per million	Population	Proportion age over 60
UK	1,290,195	50,928	749	68,017,319	15%
Congo	5,379	92	17	5,566,982	3.7%
Madagascar	17,223	249	9	27,946,942	4%
Togo	2,605	60	7	8,348,674	4.2%
Chad	1,578	100	6	16,594,682	3.9%
Equatorial	5,104	85	60	1,419,407	4.5%
Tanzania	509	21	0.3	60,343,778	3.6%

If we take into account the proportion of the population over 60 in the UK compared to a country like Madagascar then the factor of deaths per million is still 21 times the number of deaths per million of population. Hence it remains clear that the initial claims made by the Prime Minister of Madagascar should have been taken more seriously. Instead the

world listened to the advice from the W.H.O. who made such spurious statements that reliance on untested remedies could damage the nation; in that -- people may not be so keen to take precautions about catching the virus.

Let's unpick this statement. All nations are hoping for a vaccination against covid 19. This remedy, if effective, will allow whole nations to return to normal. But 'normal' means that the population need no longer take precautions against contracting the virus. This is same as the effect of relying on artemisia annua when it was known by the Madagascans that it was effective against covid 19. So what was the value in the statement made by W.H.O. Clearly whoever made that statement did not think it through.

Also we should note here that artemisia annua does more than a vaccine can do. If a person gets a serious illness from covid 19 there is no value in giving that person a vaccine. Artemisia annua also helps an infected person to fight the infection.

I can add to the above and say that now (December 2020) as vaccines are becoming available, there is still a huge role for the use of artemisia annua.

- (A) To role out the vaccines will take up to a year or more for sufficient immunity to be of significance;
- (B) The occurrence of mutant strains of the covid 19 virus may spoil the efficacy of the new vaccines;
- (C) A large percentage of populations will not take up the availability of the vaccines due to doubts or resistance to solutions provided by "big pharma".

For at least these three reasons the use of the harmless but fully effective remedy of artemisia annua will close the gaps which the modern medicines cannot close.

Addendum Four (April 2020)

APRIL 2021 - COVID 19 VARIANTS

This addendum is necessary in respect of the impact of the South African variant of the covid 19 virus, which has impacted on the Madagascan island and their use of Artemisia Annua as a covid 19 remedy. Their use of Artemisia Annua has been undermined.

South Africa, along with other countries which have malaria problems, have always used Artemisia Annua derivatives to treat malaria and other respiratory diseases. This included the epidemic of

SARS in the early 21st century. Hence their intervention treatment of covid 19 used two compounds produced by western styled pharmaceutical companies which are derived from Artemisia Annua. These are (1) Artesunate-amodiaquine and (2) Pyronaridine-artesunate. These substances have been approved by WHO. It is most likely that the commercial production of these has involved a chemical synthesis of the derivatives.

As we know all viruses have the ability to mutate and survive any attempt to eliminate them. Covid 19 is no exception. It would appear that the use of the two Artemisia Annua derivatives along with other intervention medications has caused a covid 19 variant to develop which was first identified in South Africa; now called the South African variant.

Due to the variant arising under the use of the artesunate drugs used in South Africa, this covid 19 variant developed a resistance to the Artemisia Annua treatment used by the Madagascan people. Hence their use of the herbal remedy has had to be reviewed.

This shows that the western idea that substances can be replicated from herbal remedies by chemical synthesis can produce damaging side effects. Damaging that is the traditional use of herbal remedies. The two systems of medicine should not be mixed in this western way, as the outcome which has been shown above cannot be predicted or avoided.

The western based comments on this have erroneously stated that the Madagascan use of Artemisia Annua was not successful. But these comments do not include all the knowledge behind the effect of the South African variant as stated above.

I rest my case. - Dr. A.W.P.

END OF PAPER

The beauty you see in the world comes from Him who exists within you.

Without His presence within, you would not see anything, even that beauty.

First know that your-Self is Him, then no one thing will seem to be more beautiful than any other thing. You will know that He is all things.

Then you have true Self-knowledge. This is the purpose of your life.

When you have finished with the worldly things, don't forget to remember yourself, and to forget the world. Otherwise in the end your life is truly empty.

To make your life full, study the scriptures which teach the above truth of life.

Have faith and trust that their knowledge will give you eternal peace.

Swami Vishnu Ananda Saraswati